

Preserving Culture through Traditional Performance of Rituals and Folk-Dances among Sonowal-Kachari Tribe and its Conservation Practices in the Tribal Society.

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Assam is the hub of various tribes of people belonging to different background with their unique traditions and culture. The Sonowal-Kacharis are one of the royal dynasties of the North-East and one of a branch of great Bodo-Kacharis, a major Tribal community in Assam. Sonowal-Kachari is a tribe who is rich in the characteristics in their traditions along with their arts and culture. In the present study, an attempt has been made to explore the distinctiveways of preserving the cultureof sonowal-Kacharithrough traditional performance and its conservation practices in the tribal society. This paper will provide the in-depth study on varietyof culture and traditionsof Sonowal-Kacharies in distinctivefields such as: Rituals, Folk-songs, and Folk-Dances. In the past, these Rituals, Folk-Songs and Folk-dances were performed only during festivals or on special occasionsin accordance with strict rules and regulations. However, in recent times, it has been observed that the policy has been relaxed and measures have been taken to perform these rituals, songs and dances in front of everyone for the purpose of preserving, disseminating and conserving these cultural elements among the Sonowal-Kachari tribe. The study is based on secondary sources of data which include journals, books, megazines, newspapers and internet sources etc. Descriptive researchmethod is used as the method of this research study

Keywords: Cultural Preservation, Conservation Practice, Sonowal-Kachari, Tribal Society, Ritual, Folk-Song, Folk-Dance.